

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN PURCHASING FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

Purpose – This paper analyzes how information technology (IT) can help explain performance by the purchasing function. In addition to analyzing the direct effect and mediating role of purchasing practices in the relationship between IT and purchasing performance, as has been considered in previous research, this study investigates the possibility of a moderating effect of IT in the relationships between purchasing practices and purchasing performance.

Methodology – The propositions are tested with data from 156 purchasing managers, collected through a survey of members of the Spanish Association of Professionals of Purchasing and Supply Management who work in industrial companies.

Findings – Although IT investments exert a positive effect on the purchasing function, the results show that this effect takes place through the implementation of purchasing practices that, in turn, improve the results of the purchasing function.

Originality/value – Instead of focusing on a single, specific effect of IT investment in the purchasing function, this paper considers three potential effects (direct, mediated, and moderating). Thus, it provides a more comprehensive overview of the topic and a more complete elucidation of the actual effects.

Keywords Information technology, Purchasing, Purchasing techniques

Paper type Research paper

1. Introduction

Although they may have been somewhat slow in doing so, companies now recognize the purchasing function as an important resource that helps them achieve high levels of quality, reliability, and cost savings (Carr and Pearson, 2002), as well as identify other capacities, such as flexibility and product development through collaboration with suppliers and inter-functional teams (Carter et al., 1998). With this recognition, firms increasingly request tools to support more efficient deployments of operational and strategic competencies. An operational and strategic redesign along these lines often demands information technology (IT) tools with demonstrated effectiveness (Lee et al., 2011). For example, supporting computers and specialized software can improve internal communications and supplier relations (Stump and Sriram, 1997; Paulraj et al., 2008). Parallel logistics activities benefit particularly from IT, which expand the possibilities for sharing technology and information with suppliers (Ellram, 1991; Rantala and Hilmola, 2005). In addition, IT can improve communications and coordination, which enhance the development of joint activities that can store, process and transmit information and accelerate inter-organizational activities (Clemons and Row, 1992; Sriram and Stump, 2004). The increasing use of IT thus highlights the importance of the purchasing function in terms of supplier relations and reflects the demand for tools that can facilitate communication, information exchanges (Carr and Pearson, 1999; Humphreys et al., 2005), and the allocation, evaluation, and control of various responsibilities (Carr and Smeltzer, 1999).

If we assume that using IT resources enhances purchasing performance, we next need to determine how, a **question only partially addressed in prior research**. González-Benito (2007) proposes IT as an antecedent of the implementation of certain purchasing practices, which then drive better performance. In this sense, practices serve as mediators of the relationship between IT and the operational results achieved by the purchasing function. However, IT also might act as a moderator of the relationship between practices and purchasing performance, such that the relationship grows stronger with more IT investments. To the best of our knowledge though, **no empirical research has sought to verify this potential effect**. Accordingly, we **simultaneously** address **two** possible effects of IT, in an attempt to clarify the exact role that IT plays for the purchasing function.

In so doing, we replicate and extend prior work by González-Benito (2007). As Frohlich and Dixon (2006) recommend, replication research is vital for establishing the validity of new theories. By testing such a theory in a new empirical setting and with a different sample, we help define the generalizability of previous findings. Although our replication thus constitutes a significant contribution, we also incorporate an analysis of the moderating effect of IT into this study, in an attempt to determine if such an effect exists. In so doing, we also advance understanding of the ideal configuration of purchasing functions.

Furthermore, beyond offering a concurrent analysis of mediating and moderating effects, we distinguish empirically among different types of purchasing practices, different types of IT applied in purchasing and various dimensions of operational purchasing performance. Therefore, we can depict the inter-relations of IT, purchasing practices and purchasing performance, and then identify which practices and technologies produce a particular purchasing capability. From a practical perspective, our results should help managers exploit the full potential of IT. Knowing that IT is important is not enough; companies also need to recognize how and when to use different forms of IT. By determining whether IT is a necessary antecedent of the successful implementation of certain practices or else a good tool to leverage existing practices, we can identify the optimal moments for adopting IT and the proper way to introduce new purchasing strategies.

The rest of the paper is organized in four sections. In Section 2, we introduce several purchasing practices and offer an initial hypothesis about their relationship with purchasing performance. We then hypothesize about direct and indirect effects of IT. We describe the methodology used to test these hypotheses in Section 4, and then present the results in Section 5. Finally, we conclude with a summary of our main findings.

2. Advanced Purchasing Practices: Initial Hypothesis

The evolution of the purchasing function has led to the development of new relationships with suppliers (Hansen, 2009; Matthyssens and Van den Bulte, 1994) that do not fit with a traditional image of suppliers as adversaries (Helper, 1991) and instead establish new forms of cooperation. This change often stems from the implementation of strategic supplier development activities, which allow buyers and suppliers to combine and exchange knowledge, resources and capabilities synergistically and in turn permit the realization of rents and performance improvements (Sánchez-Rodríguez, 2009). Companies that are willing to share knowledge and resources also can generate more income than is possible individually (Dyer and Singh, 1998). Collaborative trends thus reflect the firms' efforts to develop improve their performance by creating climates of trust and stronger cooperation, such as through longer contracts with select suppliers (Guimaraes et al., 2002; Janda and Seshadri, 2005; Liao et al., 2012). Such efforts have attracted growing acceptance and implementation, particularly in the purchasing function, as outlined in the previous studies we summarize in Table 1.

Prior research also indicates that the implementation of such practices has positive effects for the organization (Gimenez and Ventura, 2005; Kannan and Choon, 2006; Modi and Mabert, 2007; Prajogo et al., 2012; Prajogo and Olhager, 2012). Krause (1999) concludes that control practices, such as the assessment and certification of suppliers, can help ensure the regular and systematized implementation of quality standards, which improves overall product quality. Carr and Pearson (1999)

note that greater involvement practices, such as personnel exchanges with suppliers or better training, ultimately can lower costs, improve quality and increase coordination, which then enhances flexibility and reliability. Similarly, greater coordination and logistics integration enable companies to achieve cost reductions, quality improvements and faster delivery times (Chen and Paulraj, 2004; Gimenez and Ventura, 2005; Prajogo et al., 2012; Prajogo and Olhager, 2012). In their review, Van der Vaart and Van Donk (2008) reveal that empirical literature has documented a consistent positive relationship between supply chain integration and performance; Li et al. (2009) provide additional evidence of the positive effects of supply chain integration. In the quality management research tradition, Sanchez-Rodríguez and Martínez-Lorente (2005) also show empirically that different elements of a quality management strategy for purchasing correlate significantly with various performance measures. Some of these elements include the practices mentioned in Figure 1, in indirect support of their beneficial effects. In line with this evidence, we propose:

H₁: The implementation of advanced purchasing management practices positively relates to the performance of the purchasing function.

3. The Role of IT in Purchasing and Supply Management

3.1. Direct effect of IT on purchasing performance

Beyond its unique contributions to productivity (i.e., the “productivity paradox”; Brynjolfsson and Hitt, 1996), IT has significantly contributed to the processing, storage and distribution of information and greatly modified the form of transactions. For the purchasing function, IT represents an instrument for streamlining and simplifying task execution, which then improves performance.

For more than 30 years, systems such as Material Requirements planning (MRP), up to the current Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), have allowed a more fluid availability and integration of information inside enterprises (Kumar and Meade, 2002, Bendoly and Schoenherr, 2005). With the growth of the Internet, apart from the promotion in the use of these tools, it has facilitated that systems such as the Electronic Data Interchange (EDI), expand, and increase the flexibility of the inter-firm commercial trade as well as its processes of supply "e-Procurement" (Muffato y Payaro, 2004). Various researchers note the contributions of specific IT tools, such as electronic data interchange (EDI), enterprise resource planning (ERP), or the Internet. For example, Barnejee and Sriram (1995) consider the impact of EDI on purchases and find that it improves operational performance, because it reduces the need for supervision while also increasing the systematization, automation and simplification of order management. Zsidisin and Ellram (2001) note that companies that develop formal or informal alliances with suppliers can achieve benefits through cost reductions and quality improvements. However, achieving these benefits demands close coordination and expanded information exchanges, so companies that possess tools such as EDI, extranets, Intranet capabilities or ERP enjoy better positioning. Scala and McGrath (1993) also conclude that by using technologies

such as EDI, companies can achieve significant process improvements. According to Wu et al. (2006), the effect of IT on supply chain capabilities is positive and leads to improved financial and marketing performance. Similarly, Rajaguru and Matanda (2012) provide evidence of the positive effect of inter-organizational information systems on relevant capabilities. Likewise, Wu et al., (2007) found that through the use of coordination and transactional e-procurement applications can directly improve efficiency for the firms (e.g. increasing amount and frequency of information exchange between trading partners, reducing human errors and increasing the speed of processing real-time purchasing orders). In general, IT supports communication links between suppliers and buyers, which translate into significant reductions in transaction costs (Lin and Pervan, 2003), greater flexibility (Gunasekaran and Ngai, 2004), and more reliability in purchasing activities (Sriram and Stump, 2004). Therefore, we propose:

H₂: IT investments in the purchasing function relate positively to the performance of the purchasing function.

3.2 Indirect effect of IT: The mediating role of advanced purchasing practices

Although we propose a direct positive impact of IT on purchasing performance, the real challenge is to determine how this effect takes place. We might investigate the relationship between IT and purchasing performance by identifying variables that mediate the relationship in H₂; similarly, previous authors (Dehning and Richardson, 2002; González-Benito, 2007; Sriram and Stump, 2004) have examined the mediating role of purchasing management practices on the relationship between IT investments and operational results for the purchasing function. Li et al. (2009) cite a mediating role of supply chain integration in the relationship between the implementation of IT and supply chain performance; Prajogo and Olhager (2012) focus on logistics integration and provide evidence of its mediating role in the connection of performance to IT connections with suppliers. We follow and extend this argument by suggesting that IT facilitates the implementation of advanced practices in the purchasing function, and these practices in turn improve its performance and thus indirectly the performance of the whole organization. As Hemsworth et al. (2005) argue, IT investments in general help improve complex relationships with suppliers and integrate purchasing with other areas of the organization. For example, IT can implement control activities and supplier monitoring, because the deployment of communication tools enables purchasers to maintain contacts with and engage in ongoing monitoring of suppliers, ensuring prompt responses to any supply problems or failures (Sriram and Stump, 2004). Thus, IT provides better supplier control and monitoring, which facilitates more efficient, reliable, smaller supplier bases (Carr and Pearson, 1999; Humphreys et al., 2005). Similarly, the development of supplier involvement and logistics integration practices become more feasible when data-sharing systems already exist (Dewhurst et al. 1999), because they improve the

accuracy and speed of routine interactions (Hou and Huang, 2006; Mukhopadhyay et al., 1995) and increase the exchange of strategic and tactical information facilitated via e-procurement applications that promote interorganizational coordination (Mukhopadhyay and Kekre, 2002)

Therefore, the use of IT, from basic systems to the most advanced communications with suppliers, could be functionally useful in terms of implementing advanced purchasing practices effectively. We propose:

H₃: IT investments in the purchasing function relate positively to the implementation of advanced practices in that function, such that the implementation of the practices mediates the relationship between IT investments and the purchasing function's performance.

3.3 Indirect effect of IT: Moderating role between practices and performance

A third route to understanding the positive effects of IT in the purchasing function that has not been previously explored would refer to their ability to enhance and even transform the positive effects associated with the performance of other elements in the purchasing function. In this sense, IT would moderate the relationship between these elements and their outcomes. In other contexts, IT appears to act as a moderator that influences organizational performance; for example, in a case study, Dewett and Jones (2001) highlight IT's moderating effect on the impacts of organizational structure, size, learning, culture, and inter-organizational relationships.

We argue in turn that IT should positively moderate the relationship between advanced practices and the performance of the purchasing function. For example, logistics activities might benefit from the application of IT, which increases the possibilities for technology and information sharing with suppliers (Ellram, 1991) and thereby minimizes coordination problems, enhancing organizational flexibility and responsiveness while minimizing risk and inventory costs (Hartono et al., 2010). The efficiency and effectiveness of activities, such as formal evaluation, monitoring, and control over suppliers' operations, also might be increased through the use of IT (Sriram and Stump, 2004), in that IT facilitates more direct, faster contacts with suppliers to identify flaws in or changes to the supply. This potential of IT is also highlighted by Roy and Sivakumar (2007), who identify it as a relevant driver of globalization, because IT facilitates the organization, supervision and control of remote suppliers. The effect of supplier involvement activities also should improve, because IT can generate synergies and enhance teamwork across organizations by establishing networks of communication and consultation during joint product design and development processes, especially if this effective communication enhances perceptions of trust and switching costs (Yen et al., 2011). With this reasoning, we propose:

H₄: IT investments positively moderate the relationship between the implementation of advanced practices and performance by the purchasing function, such that the effect of the implementation of advanced practices on the purchasing function's performance increases with greater IT investments.

Figure 1 provides a graphical representation of our proposed hypotheses.

4. Methodology

4.1. Data

The population chosen to provide a test of these hypotheses consisted of all Spanish firms belonging to industrial sectors. To obtain representative information of this population, we sent a questionnaire to the members of the Spanish Association of Purchasing and Supply (AERCE). At the time of this study (first quarter of 2008), this association included 2,459 industrial members, who accounted for 71% of the total membership. The questionnaire appeared on a web page, with a link to the page in an AERCE newsletter. **These newsletters are regularly sent to all members.** With this procedure, we obtained 156 completed questionnaires, for a response rate of 6.34%, which is **similar to that achieved by prior surveys of purchasing professionals (e.g., Ellis et al., 2010).**

4.2. Measures

4.2.1. Advanced purchasing practices. The purchasing managers assessed, on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = “never,” 7 = “in all cases”), the level of their implementation of representative practices within each category in Figure 1 (control practices, participation, logistics). A confirmatory factor analysis revealed whether the three groups of practices constituted independent dimensions; the results were unsatisfactory. Therefore, we conducted an exploratory factor analysis with Varimax rotation to determine if the data corresponded to other factors that we had not considered in our theoretical development. The results of this analysis, in Table 2, indicated that involvement practices loaded on two factors: supplier involvement in product design and production processes.

We reapplied a confirmatory factor analysis to distinguish these two factors (see Table 2). The indices that we used to assess the adjustment of the proposed model to the observed data structure reached or approached the recommended values; all four factors exhibited Cronbach's alphas greater than 0.7, indicating acceptable reliability. Therefore, the measurement model distinguishing four factors offered an acceptable fit. By calculating the average of the items used for each factor, we built four measures of the purchasing practices' implementation: control practices, supplier involvement in product design, supplier involvement in production processes, and logistics practices.

4.2.2. *Purchasing operational performance.* The purchasing manager respondents also indicated, again on seven-point Likert scales (1 = “much worse,” 4 = “equal to,” 7 = “much better”) the progress that the purchasing function had achieved in the previous three years on the issues listed in Table 3. According to Hemsworth et al. (2005) and Li et al. (2006), the four competitive priorities raised by Wheelwright (1978) (quality, cost, dependability, flexibility) are the most reliable for determining the performance of the purchasing function. Therefore, we selected three items to represent the quality objective, two that refer to the cost objective, three for dependability, and two for flexibility. A confirmatory factor analysis produced similar results to those obtained for the advanced purchasing practices (see Table 3). We thus assert that the observed data fit the model that distinguishes four competitive priorities or objectives.

4.2.3. *IT investment.* We asked the managers to rate, on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = “not at all,” 7 = “largely”) the extent to which the statements in Table 4 described the reality at their companies. Following Sriram et al. (1997), we used three items to refer to base systems, two to describe specific systems that could manage purchases, and three items that involve communications with suppliers. A confirmatory factor analysis revealed that the three kinds of technologies represented independent dimensions. The supplier communication systems achieved a low Cronbach’s α value; however, considering its strong confirmation by Sriram et al. (1997) and Hemsworth et al. (2005), we chose to retain it for our analysis.

4.3. Analysis and results

To test H_1 – H_3 , we applied structural equation modeling with AMOS 19.0. We computed second-order factors to capture all the performance dimensions and IT investment dimensions. The four models we studied represented each of the dimensions of advanced purchasing practices (control, involvement in design, involvement in processes, and logistics). Table 5 contains the goodness-of-fit indexes of the four models; Figure 2 depicts one of them in greater detail.

As we can observe in Table 5, the goodness-of-fit indexes, both absolute and incremental, exceeded or approached the recommended values, so we assumed acceptable fit for the models and proceeded to evaluate the coefficients. These coefficients indicated a positive relationship between the implementation of advanced purchasing practices and purchasing performance (see the last column in Table 5), in clear support of H_1 . The result also is consistent with previous studies that affirm the beneficial effects of the practices listed in Table 1 (e.g., Carr and Pearson, 1999; Chen and Paulraj, 2004; Narisimhan and Das, 2001; Zsidisin and Ellram, 2001). The effect of all three forms of IT (i.e., base systems, purchasing-specific systems, communication systems) on the implementation of three advanced purchasing practices (i.e., control activities, involvement in processes, activities logistics) were positive and significant at a minimum confidence level of 95%. This finding, combined with our

confirmation of H₁, reveals that these three practices mediate the relationship between IT investment and purchasing performance, in support of H₃. Nonetheless, we did not find any significant effect of IT on involvement practices in product design, so not all advanced purchasing practices have such a mediating role. In this sense, we cannot offer complete or unequivocal support for H₃, but we consider this hypothesis valid, in that it applies for most of the advanced purchasing practices we investigate.

Regarding the direct effect of IT on the purchasing performance dimensions, we find from Table 5 that the coefficients were not significant in any cases; we therefore reject H₂. Mediation by advanced purchasing practices might represent the link between these two variables; our analysis indicates an indirect effect of IT on purchasing performance, channeled through the implementation of advanced purchasing practices.

To test H₄, we applied a moderated regression analysis (Sharma et al. 1981). First, we created interaction variables by computing the product of each dimension of IT investment (IT_i, i=1, 2, 3) and each dimension of advanced purchasing practices (APP_j). Second, for each pair (IT_i× APP_j) and each dimension of purchasing performance, we estimated four models: (1) control variables (firm size, industry type) as independent variables; (2) including APP_j; (3) including IT_i; and (4) incorporating the interaction effect (IT_i×APP_j). To confirm the existence of positive moderating effects, the fourth model should offer significantly greater predictive power (R²), and the interaction term should exhibit a positive, significant coefficient in this model.

In Table 6 we list cases for which we found a moderate relationship in our estimates of 48 possibilities (12 IT_i×APP_j pairs for each purchasing performance dimension). We found few such cases; in three of them, the moderation appears negative. There were only two cases of positive moderation. At a confidence level of 10%, 4.8 of the 48 models studied thus may be significant before we must waive the null hypothesis. That is, there is insufficient evidence to support H₄

5. Discussion

i.e., base systems, purchasing-specific systems, communication systems) on the implementation of three advanced purchasing practices (i.e., control activities, involvement in processes, activities logistics)

Our results indicate that IT investments (i.e., base systems, purchasing-specific systems, communication systems) are relevant for the implementation of advanced practices in the purchasing function. In particular, IT plays an important role for the implementation of control, involvement in the processes, and logistics practices; in general, it supports the implementation of advanced practices

in the purchasing function, which then leads to several improvements. This result is consistent with the conclusions offered by Stump and Sriram (1997) and Ellram and Zsidisin (2002). However, in Table 5, we find no significant effect of IT on involvement practices in design, probably because such involvement demands specific technologies that relate to technical aspects of the product and its components—that is, aspects that the IT dimensions we consider do not address. An alternative explanation might be that the involvement of suppliers in the design and development of new products have major implications for other departments (e.g., marketing), which provide information about market trends and customers' needs and preferences. In this sense, the adoption of IT probably is not specific to the purchasing function, a condition that is not captured by our constructs in Table 4.

Our results also reject a direct effect of IT on purchasing (H_2), though we find an effect on the implementation of advanced purchasing practices and through them an influence on purchasing performance (H_1 , H_3). Therefore, the effect of IT on purchasing outcomes is not direct but contingent, consistent with Powell and Dent-Micallef's (1997) conclusion that IT alone cannot produce competitive advantages, even though it serves as a means to leverage other resources that can build these advantages. Similarly, Ryssel et al., (2004, p. 204) note "the existence of IT in an organization or relationship does not guarantee the creation of additional value". Therefore, we cannot fully understand the effects of IT if we do not identify the mediators through which its effects are channeled and the tools that help leverage the potential of IT. Our research contributes to identifying and confirming that advanced purchasing practices serve as one such mediator. The results are consistent with Gonzalez-Benito's (2007) recognition of the relevance of the strategic integration of the purchasing function as a means to understand the link between IT and purchasing performance. Similarly, other authors cite mediating roles of supply chain capabilities (Wu et al., 2006), supply chain integration (Li et al., 2009) and logistics integration (Prajogo and Olhager, 2012) in the relationship between IT and performance. Therefore, implementing IT in the purchasing function, without further action, is not really useful, because IT is mainly a facilitator.

With regard to H_4 , which suggests a moderating effect of IT on the relationship between purchasing practices and purchasing performance, we show in Table 6 that with the exception of a few specific situations, there is no evidence that IT plays a significant moderating role. Therefore, its influence on the purchasing function appears limited to driving the implementation of advanced practices. It is important to highlight this question as a central contribution of our study. Previous research has focused on identifying mediators between IT and performance but not on the moderating effects of IT. Although we were unable to demonstrate such moderating effects, we advance extant literature by demonstrating their absence, at least with the statistical power of our study (given by the sample size). Reporting only confirmed hypotheses represents a publishing bias that leaves the field with information solely about confirmed relationships between variables. Although this article does not

introduce more new attributes of IT than previously identified, we establish that IT does not have a moderating effect on the relationship between advanced purchasing practices and purchasing performance.

In turn, these results prompt us to enter the debate about the “productivity paradox,” as proposed by Nobel laureate Robert Solow, who refers to how much and in which ways companies actually benefit from IT investments. In this debate, the resource-based view of the firm offers some explanation about the disparity in results: Perhaps the outcomes in prior research depended not on the resources used but rather on the available capabilities to combine and use those resources. Technological resources then enhance firm success because they enable the integration of human resources and existing business resources to achieve a competitive advantage that reflects the firm’s specific attributes (Keen, 1993). For the purchasing function, this advantage would be based on the possibility of developing advanced practices (control and monitoring of suppliers, supplier involvement in production processes, integrated logistics) and combining them with a coordinated, consistent set of technologies (Thomas, 1995).

If we focus on logistics integration, the results prove that a seamless supply chain requires a fluid flow of information between buyers and suppliers. This flow reduces uncertainty and contributes to the generation of trust and long-term relationships, which are crucial to efforts to integrate production processes into the supply chain (Prajogo and Olhager, 2012). Trust is also the basis for suppliers’ involvement in their customers’ production processes. Therefore, IT can be regarded as a tool to generate mutual commitment and trust in the supply chain.

In relation to control practices, our results reveal a connection between IT and quality management. Supplier assessment involves the collection and processing of information from suppliers; the adoption of IT makes these tasks easier. Trust also has an important role in quality control practices, in that it facilitates access to information about suppliers’ internal operations. Again, the potential of IT to generate trust could be a valid explanation for the relationships between IT and advanced purchasing practices. However, selecting partners with similar business goals and management style, because of their high levels of organizational compatibility, may increase the interaction quality and thus the technology transfer success, (Leischnig, et al., 2013)

In terms of business practice, managers should keep in mind that implementing IT in the purchasing function contributes to the development of advanced purchasing practices. More sophisticated purchasing systems lead to improved performance by the purchasing function. However, technology investments cannot be seen as an end in themselves. They represent instead the means or bases to build better management. Investment does not produce results, but it can be exploited to build a more

sophisticated supply management system though. At the same time, managers cannot ignore the importance of selecting appropriate suppliers. As Rajaguru and Matanda (2012) show, the technical, strategic and cultural compatibility of an organization with its suppliers is crucial for ensuring the optimal use of IT. Similarly, suppliers' use of internal IT can facilitate their application of shared IT with their purchasing organizations (Ryssel et al., 2004).

Although we have focused on inter-organizational, rather than intra-organizational, IT, managers should consider that our reasoning likely applies in internal settings too. The possibility of introducing IT to enhance intra-organizational relationships, communications and information exchanges—between purchasing and marketing departments in particular—could facilitate the implementation of innovative purchasing practices and the creation of economic benefits. As Buvik (2001, p. 447) notes, “organizational learning and coordination within firms based on better and more frequent interactions between the marketing department and the purchasing staff might provide significant knowledge about supply and buying behavior which could be incorporated in both purchasing operations and supply strategies.” Sheth et al. (2009) accordingly predict that marketing and purchasing departments will become closer, as a result of the shift from product- to capability-focused commerce.

Our results not only help managers understand the potential of IT for the purchasing function but also indicate that purchasing managers interested in implementing advanced purchasing practices might confront unexpected barriers, if they lack an adequate level of IT. Plainly, advanced purchasing practices might not be accessible to every organization; their IT capabilities determine this accessibility.

6. Conclusions

This research examines the role of IT in the purchasing function, paying special attention to the practices and results achieved. Our analyses provide evidence of a positive effect of advanced purchasing practices on the results attained by the purchasing function. Therefore, the implementation of advanced purchasing practices, such as supplier control, suppliers' participation in product or process design and logistics integration, all significantly contribute to improve quality, cost, flexibility and reliability outcomes.

Yet our research does not confirm a direct relationship between IT investment and purchasing performance. The three dimensions of IT investment related to the purchasing function (base systems, specific purchasing systems, and communication systems) do not generate any effect for purchasing performance by themselves. Similarly, we found insufficient evidence that these same dimensions might exert a moderating effect on the relationship between purchasing practices and performance.

Instead, our results categorically establish that IT can enhance the implementation of advanced purchasing practices that improve the quality, cost, flexibility or reliability of supply. Overall we show that IT investments are important prerequisites for the development of the purchasing function, and through this development, it is possible to improve the performance of the purchasing function. These results also are consistent with those described in previous research (e.g., Gonzalez-Benito, 2007; Li et al., 2009; Prajogo and Olhager, 2012; Wu et al. 2006), but we can add that the models they propose are not incomplete simply because they excluded the moderating effects of IT. Although the performance of the purchasing function cannot be improved directly through IT, it can be enhanced through the introduction of distinctive practices. Therefore, top managers need to understand that ignoring distinctive elements could lead to perceived failures and the waste of IT investments.

Finally, our research focused on the implementation of IT in the purchasing function to support inter-organizational relationships. However, we think our arguments likely are valid for IT focused on facilitating intra-organizational interactions and communications, such as those between marketing and purchasing. We hope additional research confirms this prediction and provides empirical evidence about the effect of other types of intra-organizational IT on performance. Also, future studies could focus on more diversified enterprises and the analysis of the impact of the age of the companies in the adaptation and learning of IT and its impact on intra or inter-organizational relationships.

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Table 1: Advanced purchasing practices

CONTROL PRACTICES			
Formal evaluation of suppliers' capacities and performance	Quality certifications required of suppliers	Quality testing of purchased materials	Monitoring and controlling key suppliers' operations
Krause and Ellram (1997), Carr and Pearson (1999), Krause (1999), Narasimhan and Das (2001), Sánchez-Rodríguez et al. (2005), Kannan and Choon (2006), Wagner (2006), Prajogo et al. (2012)	Carr and Pearson (1999), Krause (1999), Hemsworth et al. (2005), Sánchez-Rodríguez et al. (2005).	Kannan and Choon (2006), Wagner (2006).	Carr and Pearson (1999), Humphreys et al. (2005), Kannan and Choon (2006), Wagner (2006).
SUPPLIER INVOLVEMENT PRACTICES			
Key suppliers are involved in improving product design	Supplier involvement in the design and development of new products	Suppliers help solve problems in the company's production processes	Suppliers involved in the design of the company's logistics system
Narasimhan and Das (2001), Chen and Paulraj (2004), Hemsworth et al. (2005), Sánchez-Rodríguez et al. (2005), Kannan and Choon (2006), Carr et al. (2008)	Narasimhan and Das (2001), Chen and Paulraj (2004), Hemsworth et al. (2005), Janda and Seshadri (2005), Sánchez-Rodríguez et al. (2005), Carr et al. (2008)	Krause (1999), Gimenez and Ventura (2005), Janda and Seshadri (2005).	Chen and Paulraj (2004), Gimenez and Ventura (2005), Kannan and Choon (2006), Oh and Rhee (2008).
LOGISTIC PRACTICES			
Coordination of manufacturing plans and production lines between suppliers and buyers	Adaptation of suppliers' delivery frequencies to buyers' requirements	Coordination of transportation and storage capacity among suppliers and buyers	Coordination in the use of containers and equipment between suppliers and buyers
Frohlich and Westbrook (2001), Gimenez and Ventura (2005), Kannan and Choon (2006), Oh and Rhee (2008), Prajogo et al. (2012).	Frohlich and Westbrook (2001), Chen and Paulraj (2004).	Chen and Paulraj (2004).	Frohlich and Westbrook (2001).

Table 2: Measures of advanced purchasing practices

		EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS				CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS						
						F1	F2	F3	F4			
CONTROL PRACTICES												
ACTCONT1	FORMAL EVALUATION OF SUPPLIERS' CAPACITIES AND PERFORMANCE	0.168	0.743	0.020	0.196	0.652						
ACTCONT2	QUALITY CERTIFICATIONS REQUIRED OF SUPPLIERS	-0.042	0.762	0.027	0.225	0.411						
ACTCONT3	QUALITY TESTING OF PURCHASED MATERIALS	0.290	0.599	0.315	-0.289	0.540						
ACTCONT4	MONITORING AND CONTROLLING KEY SUPPLIERS' OPERATIONS	0.493	0.616	0.175	0.015	0.848						
SUPPLIER INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCT DESIGN												
ACTPAR1	KEY SUPPLIERS ARE INVOLVED IN IMPROVING PRODUCT DESIGN	0.141	0.120	0.891	0.159		0.812					
ACTPAR2	SUPPLIER INVOLVEMENT IN THE DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF NEW PRODUCTS	0.223	0.093	0.882	0.183		0.939					
SUPPLIER INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCTION PROCESS												
ACTPAR3	SUPPLIERS HELP SOLVE PROBLEMS OF THE COMPANY'S PRODUCTION PROCESSES	0.193	0.070	0.294	0.705			0.755				
ACTPAR4	SUPPLIERS INVOLVED IN THE DESIGN OF THE COMPANY'S LOGISTICS SYSTEM	0.189	0.197	0.083	0.849			0.718				
LOGISTICS PRACTICES												
ACTLOG1	COORDINATION OF MANUFACTURING PLANS AND PRODUCTION LINES BETWEEN SUPPLIERS AND BUYERS	0.641	0.273	0.162	0.189				0.678			
ACTLOG2	ADAPTATION OF SUPPLIERS' DELIVERY FREQUENCIES TO BUYERS' REQUIREMENTS	0.836	0.125	0.089	0.015				0.713			
ACTLOG3	COORDINATION OF TRANSPORTATION AND STORAGE CAPACITY AMONG SUPPLIERS AND BUYERS	0.794	0.037	0.230	0.227				0.789			
ACTLOG4	COORDINATION IN THE USE OF CONTAINERS AND EQUIPMENT BETWEEN SUPPLIERS AND BUYERS	0.574	0.107	0.076	0.432				0.606			
CRONBACH'S ALPHA						0.700	0.865	0.700	0.775			
F1: CONTROL PRACTICES	CORRELATIONS				F1							
F2: SUPPLIER INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCT DESIGN					F2					0.407***		
F3: SUPPLIER INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCTION PROCESS					F3					0.416***	0.503***	
F4: LOGISTICS PRACTICES					F4					0.649***	0.515***	0.604***
VARIMAX ROTATION						INDEX	R.V.*	VALUES OBTAINED				
EXPLAINED VARIANCE: 68.52%						$\chi^2/g.l.$	≤ 3	2.139				
						GFI	≥ 0.90	0.905				
						AGFI	≥ 0.80	0.845				
						TLI	≥ 0.90	0.884				
						CFI	≥ 0.90	0.916				

*** $p < 0.01$. ** $p < 0.05$. * $p < 0.10$.

*Recommended values based on Chau (1997)

Table 3: Measures of purchasing performance

		CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS			
		F1	F2	F3	F4
QUALITY					
PFC1	RELIABILITY OF PURCHASED PRODUCTS	0.850			
PFC2	FIT BETWEEN PURCHASING SPECIFICATIONS AND PURCHASING PRODUCTS (HIGH FINISH, UNIFORMITY,...)	0.698			
PFC3	EFFICACY OF SUPPLIERS IN ATTENDING TO COMPLAINTS	0.582			
COST					
PFC4	COST OF PURCHASES		0.602		
PFC5	LOW INVENTORY LEVELS		0.599		
DEPENDABILITY					
PFC6	TIME NEEDED TO FULFILL ORDERS (LEAD TIME)			0.846	
PFC7	FULFILLMENT OF AGREED SCHEDULES BY SUPPLIERS			0.857	
PFC8	FULFILLMENT OF AGREED DELIVERY REQUIREMENTS BY SUPPLIERS (QUANTITY, QUALITY, FORMAT...)			0.879	
FLEXIBILITY					
PFC9	SUPPLIER CAPABILITY TO INTRODUCE (CUSTOMIZED) CHANGES IN PRODUCTS				0.880
PFC10	SUPPLIER RATE OF INTRODUCTION OF NEW PRODUCTS (UPDATED AND LEADING PRODUCTS)				0.712
CRONBACH'S ALPHA		0.747	0.530	0.894	0.770
F1: QUALITY	CORRELATIONS	F1			
F2: COST		F2	0.745***		
F3: DEPENDABILITY		F3	0.836***	0.650***	
F4: FLEXIBILITY		F4	0.544***	0.363***	0.617***
		INDEX	R.V.+	VALUES OBTAINED	
		X ² /g.l.	≤ 3	1.726	
		GFI	≥ 0.90	0.942	
		AGFI	≥ 0.80	0.890	
		TLI	≥ 0.90	0.954	
		CFI	≥ 0.90	0.970	

*** $p < 0.01$ ** $p < 0.05$ * $p < 0.10$

*Recommended values based on Chau (1997)

Table 4. Measures of IT investment

		CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS		
		F1	F2	F3
BASE SYSTEMS				
TIC1	THE HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE USED IN THE PURCHASING DEPARTMENT ARE FREQUENTLY UPDATED AND RENEWED	0.800		
TIC2	THE PURCHASING PERSONNEL HAS ADVICE AND SUPPORT FOR THE USE OF IT AT THEIR DISPOSAL	0.867		
TIC3	THE PURCHASING DEPARTMENT HAS PERIPHERAL EQUIPMENT FOR THEIR EXCLUSIVE USE (PRINTERS, SCANNERS, ...)	0.491		
SPECIFIC SYSTEMS FOR PURCHASING MANAGEMENT				
TIC4	OUR INTERNAL NETWORKS ARE ADAPTED FOR THE EMISSION AND MONITORING OF PURCHASING ORDERS AND TO SUPPORT OTHER PURCHASING ACTIVITIES		0.786	
TIC5	WE HAVE SOFTWARE TO MANAGE DIVERSE PURCHASING ACTIVITIES (RECEPTION AND CONTROL OF SHIPMENTS, INVENTORY CONTROL)		0.784	
COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS SUPPLIER				
TIC6	OUR PURCHASING DEPARTMENT HAS THE NECESSARY EQUIPMENT FOR ELECTRONIC COMMUNICATION WITH SUPPLIERS			0,707
TIC7	OUR PURCHASING SOFTWARE IS COMPATIBLE WITH THAT OF SUPPLIERS AND ALLOWS INFORMATION SHARING (COSTS, ORDER STATUS, PRODUCT SPECIFICATIONS, INVOICING, ...)			0,460
TIC8	WE HAVE THE NECESSARY SOFTWARE TO MAKEMONEY TRANSFERS AND PAYMENTS TO SUPPLIERS			0,456
CRONBACH'S ALPHA		0.742	0.754	0,546
F1: BASE SYSTEMS	CORRELATIONS	F1		
F2: SPECIFIC SYSTEMS FOR PURCHASING MANAGEMENT		F2	0.899***	
F3: COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS SUPPLIER		F3	0.697***	0,820***
		INDEX	R.V.+	VALUES OBTAINED
		X ² /g.l.	≤ 3	2.730
		GFI	≥ 0.90	0.934
		AGFI	≥ 0.80	0.861
		TLI	≥ 0.90	0.890
		CFI	≥ 0.90	0.933

*** $p < 0.01$ ** $p < 0.05$ * $p < 0.10$

*Recommended values based on Chau (1997)

Table 5. Estimation of mediation models: Goodness-of-fit indexes and coefficients

		INDEX				IT→ CONTROL PRACTICES	IT→PURCHASING PERFORMANCE	CONTROL PRACTICES → PURCHASING PERFORMANCE
		GFI	RMSE	AGFI	CFI			
Rec. Values[†]		>=0.90	<=0.08	>=0.80	>=0.90			
MEDIATING VARIABLES	CONTROL PRACTICES	0.850	0.061	0.812	0.910	0.444***	-0.011	0.270***
						IT→ INVOLVEMENT DESIGN	IT→ PURCHASING PERFORMANCE	INVOLVEMENT DESIGN→PURCHASING PERFORMANCE
	INVOLVEMENT IN DESIGN	0.859	0.062	0.818	0.923	0.182	0.080	0.158***
						IT→ INVOLVEMENT PROCESS	IT→PURCHASING PERFORMANCE	INVOLVEMENT PROCESS→PURCHASING PERFORMANCE
	INVOLVEMENT IN PROCESS	0.863	0.059	0.824	0.925	0.277**	0.049	0.228***
						IT→LOGISTIC PRACTICES	IT→PURCHASING PERFORMANCE	LOGISTIC PRACTICES →PURCHASING PERFORMANCE
LOGISTIC PRACTICES	0.835	0.067	0.793	0.898	0.452***	-0.011	0.265***	

[†]Recommended values based on Chau (1997).

*** $p < 0.01$

Table 6. Cases of significant moderation by IT

			COEFFICIENTS						R ²	F	ΔF
			CONSTANT	FIRM SIZE	TYPE OF INDUSTRY	β ₁	β ₂	β ₃			
INDEPENDENT VARIABLES ADDED TO CONTROL VARIABLES			QUALITY DEPENDENT VARIABLE								
INV. DESIGN			5.140***	0.007	-0.047	0.124***			0.055	2.950**	8.486***
INV. DESIGN	BASE SYS.		4.849***	-0.004	-0.099	0.121***	0.080		0.071	2.906**	2.675
INV. DESIGN	BASE SYS.	INV.DESIGN X BASE SYS.	2.874***	0.009	-0.096	0.543***	0.437***	-0.078**	0.104	3.467***	5.377**
			QUALITY DEPENDENT VARIABLE								
INV. PROCESS			5.253***	0.008	-0.158	0.164***			0.084	4.658***	13.599***
INV. PROCESS	BASE SYS.		5.023***	0.000	-0.196	0.157***	0.066		0.095	3.963***	1.804
INV. PROCESS	BASE SYS.	INV PROCESS x BASE SYS.	3.812***	0.016	-0.289	0.506**	0.308**	-0.062*	0.115	3.881***	3.312**
			QUALITY DEPENDENT VARIABLE								
LOGISTIC			5.035***	0.008	-0.117	0.177***			0.082	4.501***	13.128***
LOGISTIC	BASE SYS.		4.927***	0.004	-0.139	0.166***	0.039		0.085	3.511***	0.581
LOGISTIC	BASE SYS.	LOGISTIC x BASE SYS.	3.075***	0.014	-0.110	0.572**	0.365**	-0.074*	0.106	3.570***	3.564*
			FLEXIBILITY DEPENDENT VARIABLE								
CONTROL			3.260***	0.141*	0.342	0.108*			0.060	3.253**	2.813*
CONTROL	COMUNICA. S.		3.165***	0.135*	0.306	0.094	0.053		0.066	2.669**	0.924
CONTROL	COMUNICA. S.	CONTROL x COMUNICA. S.	7.055***	0.148*	0.251	-0.606**	-0.716**	0.139**	0.105	3.527***	6.565**
			FLEXIBILITY DEPENDENT VARIABLE								
LOGISTIC			3.041***	0.130*	0.284	0.210***			0.117	6.722***	12.776***
LOGISTIC	PURCHASING SYS.		3.076***	0.129*	0.299	0.214***	-0.013		0.117	5.022***	0.045
LOGISTIC	PURCHASING SYS.	LOGISTIC x PURCHASING SYS.	5.301***	0.120	0.224	-0.314	-0.349	0.085*	0.133	4.619***	2.774*

*** $p < 0.01$ ** $p < 0.05$ * $p < 0.10$.

Figure 1: Research model

Figure 2: Example estimated mediation model (involvement practices in processes)

